

Muslim Women's Perceptions of Integration, Discrimination and Identity in England: An Observational Study on Everyday Life in Birmingham

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Abstract

This study examines the strategies developed by headscarf-wearing Muslim migrant women living in Birmingham, England, to cope with perceived discrimination. Focusing on women from Eastern regions who reside in Birmingham for educational purposes, the research explores how they navigate different forms of discrimination encountered in their everyday lives. Employing an observational research method, the study analyses women's daily practices in relation to experiences of prejudice and social exclusion. Findings derived from direct observations and informal conversations reveal that some headscarf-wearing women prefer wearing surgical masks instead of the niqab. This preference reflects an awareness of potential prejudice and the development of strategies aimed at minimising negative social encounters. Participants perceive Birmingham –a city with a relatively large Muslim population– as a safer and more inclusive environment where integration can be experienced with fewer barriers. It was also observed that women are reluctant to leave the city even for travel purposes, as they associate Birmingham with a sense of safety. While participants reported a preference for single-piece, dark-coloured clothing in their countries of origin, they indicated a shift towards more layered and relatively colourful clothing choices in the host country. These practices are understood as everyday coping strategies developed in response to perceived discrimination. By situating these everyday practices within broader debates on migration, Islamophobia, and social exclusion in Europe, the study offers a deeper understanding of how Muslim migrant women perceive and negotiate their social realities in England. The findings demonstrate that headscarf-wearing Muslim migrant women are acutely aware of anti-Muslim prejudice and discrimination and develop adaptive visibility management strategies to reduce negative experiences in their daily lives

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İngiltere’de Müslüman Kadınların Entegrasyon, Ayrımcılık ve Kimlik Algıları: Birmingham’daki Gündelik Yaşam Üzerine Gözlemsel Bir Araştırma

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Özet

Bu çalışma, İngiltere'nin Birmingham kentinde yaşayan başörtülü Müslüman göçmen kadınların algılanan ayrımcılıkla başa çıkmak amacıyla geliştirdikleri stratejileri incelemektedir. Araştırma, eğitim amacıyla Birmingham'da bulunan ve Doğu coğrafyalarından gelen kadınların gündelik yaşamlarında karşılaştıkları farklı ayrımcılık biçimleriyle nasıl başa çıktıklarını ele almaktadır. Gözlemsel araştırma yöntemi kullanılan çalışmada, kadınların önyargı ve dışlanma deneyimleriyle ilişkili gündelik yaşam pratikleri analiz edilmektedir. Doğrudan gözlemler ve resmî olmayan sohbetlerden elde edilen bulgular, bazı başörtülü kadınların niqab yerine cerrahi maske kullanmayı tercih ettiklerini ortaya koymaktadır. Bu tercih, kadınların olası önyargıların farkında olduklarını ve olumsuz sosyal karşılaşmaları en aza indirmeye yönelik stratejiler geliştirdiklerini göstermektedir. Katılımcılar, görece yüksek Müslüman nüfusa sahip bir şehir olan Birmingham'ı, entegrasyonun daha az engelle deneyimlenebildiği, daha güvenli ve kapsayıcı bir ortam olarak algılamaktadır. Kadınların, daha güvenli buldukları bu kentten seyahat amacıyla dahi ayrılmak istemedikleri gözlemlenmiştir. Menşe ülkelerinde tek parça ve koyu renkli kıyafetleri tercih ettiklerini belirten kadınlar, buldukları ülkede ise parçalı ve görece daha renkli kıyafetleri tercih ettiklerini ifade etmektedir. Bu pratikler, kadınlar tarafından algılanan ayrımcılığa yanıt olarak geliştirilen gündelik başa çıkma yöntemleri olarak değerlendirilmektedir. Çalışma, bu gündelik pratikleri Avrupa'daki göç, İslamofobi ve toplumsal dışlanma tartışmaları çerçevesinde ele alarak, Müslüman göçmen kadınların İngiltere'deki toplumsal gerçekliklerini nasıl algıladıklarına ve bu gerçekliklerle nasıl müzakere ettiklerine dair daha derinlemesine bir anlayış sunmaktadır. Bulgular, başörtülü Müslüman göçmen kadınların Müslümanlara yönelik önyargı ve ayrımcılığın farkında olduklarını ve gündelik yaşamlarında olumsuz deneyimleri azaltmak amacıyla-kendi kimliklerini koruyarak- görünürlüğü yönetmeye yönelik uyumlayıcı stratejiler geliştirdiklerini göstermektedir.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The migration of Muslim immigrants to Europe has brought and is still bringing together people from diverse identities, cultures and religions. Whether forcibly displaced or not, migration can cause long-term psychological, economic, social and political problems both in the country of destination and for the migrants themselves. Problems associated with migration may also increase alongside migration itself. In the context of migration, there may be differences between the social structures of the country of origin and the country of destination. Language, religion, lifestyle, or cultural practices may vary from society to society. In this context, international migration movements relatively increase social differences in the host country. The nation-state social structure, built on the understanding of ethnic homogeneity, political unity and cultural commonality, may perceive these differences as a threat (Castles & Miller, 2008). Christian-based culture, which is dominant in Western societies, differs from Islamic culture. This situation materialises through political processes and mechanisms that seek to emphasise the distinction between ‘us’ and ‘them’ within the concept of identity politics, creating imaginary boundaries in the public sphere (Yuval-Davis, 2006; Allen & Ögtem-Young, 2020; Allen, 2021). Studies show that those perceived as ‘the other’ in Western societies face discrimination and hate crimes (EU, 2005; Aksoy, 2010; Pittaway & Bartolomei, 2001; Ahmed, 2010; Awan & Zempi, 2017; Abbas, 2019; Erat & Demirci, 2022; Sönmez, 2025). Discrimination, which refers to prejudice based on an individual’s characteristics or preferences such as race, gender, religion, language or disability, is now a global phenomenon (Krieger, 2012; Williams & Mohammed, 2009).

In European countries, individuals with a Muslim identity experience strong feelings of belonging and feeling at home in certain regions with large Muslim populations, whereas in other regions that are multicultural or have a smaller Muslim population, they experience feelings of alienation and not feeling at home (Zempi & Chakraborti, 2015; Allen, 2021). This suggests that the Muslim population in the city has an impact on individuals and can shape their perceptions and experiences. The extent to which the culture prevailing in Europe, framed by the distinction between ‘us’ and ‘them’, will be embraced by immigrant Muslims, or whether Muslims will be allowed to live their own culture within European culture, is a matter of debate. Discussions on the integration of Muslims into European culture continue under the shadow of Islamophobia and xenophobia (Esposito & Kalin, 2011; Bekar, 2018; Abbas, 2019; Weichselbaumer, 2019; Sönmez, 2025).

Muslim women who wear headscarves are more visible in public spaces than Muslim men. For this reason, they may be directly exposed to prejudice and discrimination more than Muslim men (Zempi & Chakraborti, 2015; Khan, 2022; Kebaili & Lépinard, 2024). This study first examines social attitudes toward Muslims and migrants in Western Europe, particularly in the United Kingdom. In this context, the literature focusing on the experiences of migrant Muslims is reviewed, with particular attention to rising xenophobia, prejudice, and discrimination. Subsequently, studies that

address the specific experiences of being a headscarf-wearing Muslim migrant woman in relation to discrimination are brought together, highlighting the structural and everyday challenges this group faces along the axes of public visibility, identity, and exclusion.

In the empirical section of the study, the coping strategies developed by headscarf-wearing Muslim migrant women living in Birmingham, England, in response to perceived discrimination are examined through observational methods. The observational findings are derived from women's everyday practices and natural interactions, and the data are thematically analysed using an inductive approach. Accordingly, the study aims to make visible how headscarf-wearing Muslim migrant women navigate religion- and ethnicity-based discrimination in their everyday lives, as well as the contextual dynamics underlying these practices. The central research question guiding the study is: *'What is the context behind the observed behaviours?'*

2. METHODS

This research was conducted using the naturalistic observation method in an English language course attended by international students. Observational research is an approach that allows the researcher to observe behaviours within their natural context without intervention and to systematically record events related to these behaviours. Common research techniques such as surveys or interviews are often disconnected from the context in which the behaviour occurs and may be insufficient in capturing the momentary processes, encounters, or practices of the behaviour. In contrast, observational research allows for detailed examination of behaviours within their natural setting and relational context (Patton, 2015; Denzin & Lincoln, 2018).

In this study, participant, unstructured, covert, and interpretive observation techniques were used together. In participant observation, the researcher becomes a natural part of the observation environment and collects data from within the process (Spradley, 1980; Hammersley & Atkinson, 2019). In unstructured observation, the flow of the observation process is left to the natural dynamics of the field; only the context is determined, and the observed behaviours are recorded systematically. Covert observation refers to the observed group being unaware of the research process (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). Since the primary aim of this research was to explore the question, *"What is the context behind the observed behaviours?"*, the data were analysed and interpreted using an interpretive observation approach.

The observations were conducted at an English language course attended by international students in Birmingham, the United Kingdom. The study focused on six Muslim female students who were all wearing headscarves and were enrolled in the same course. The fact that these women had similar cultural and religious backgrounds, developed similar daily practices, and shared common social positions in terms of public visibility made them a cohesive observation group. The participants

were identified by the researcher through natural interactions within the course; the group forming the sample was treated as a single unit of observation due to the development of shared behavioural patterns. While some participants knew each other, the group was generally not in contact with each other; therefore, the commonality was based on shared identity and similar practices.

Observations were carried out over a period of three months, five days per week, between 09:00 a.m. and 12:00 p.m., within classroom settings. This time frame was selected as it allowed for the observation of interactions occurring before, during, and after lessons. Throughout the observation period, the researcher systematically monitored whether behaviours were consistent over time or situational, as well as how they varied across contexts. Participants were not informed of the observation during the study period. However, naturally occurring everyday conversations were used to gain insight into how participants interpreted certain behaviours, the reasons underlying their continued practices, and the motivations shaping these practices. These interactions did not constitute formal interviews but emerged organically within daily communication.

As the study was designed as a non-interventionist observational study conducted in a routine educational setting, no formal consent procedure was implemented. The research focused exclusively on observing naturally occurring behaviours and involved minimal risk to participants. Participants’ confidentiality was maintained throughout the study, and all fieldnotes were used solely for the analysis of behavioural patterns.

The observational data were first analysed by identifying recurring behavioural patterns. Common behavioural clusters were then established across participants. An open coding process was applied to these clusters, through which similar behaviours were thematically categorised. Following this, an inductive analytical approach was employed to explore how participants produced, sustained, and adapted these behaviours in their everyday lives and under varying contextual conditions.

The researcher shares cultural and religious similarities with the participants. This positional closeness facilitated access to the field and contributed to participants perceiving the researcher as someone familiar, which encouraged more open and natural expressions of preferences, tendencies, and coping strategies during everyday interactions. While this positionality enhanced data richness, it was approached with reflexive awareness during the analytical process, and care was taken to minimise its influence on interpretation.

3. CONTEXT

From the early 20th century onwards, Muslim workers from South Asia and Africa began leaving their countries and migrating to Western Europe. The number of migrants who were forcibly displaced or left their countries voluntarily following internal political turmoil in the Middle East increased over the years. Between 2000 and 2020, the number of international migrants increased

across all continents. With 30 million international migrants, Europe experienced the second-largest increase during this period (IOM, 2021). In some European countries that are destination countries for migrants, the concept of ‘the other’ used to describe migrants is becoming widespread and this situation is fuelling xenophobia and racism (Pittaway & Bartolomei, 2001). Xenophobia is on the rise in Europe (Bekar, 2018). The primary cause of anti-immigrant prejudice and exclusionary attitudes is economic competition in areas such as the labour market and welfare system. Those who are already settled may be unwilling to share their economic prosperity. Alongside the economic threat is the possibility that local culture may be harmed by the influx of foreign culture. For this reason, cultural threat is another factor that fuels this prejudice (Gorodzeisky & Semyonov, 2019).

Given the European Convention on Human Rights, Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, Treaty of Lisbon, International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination and Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Intolerance and of Discrimination Based on Religion or Belief, one might assume that discrimination does not exist in European countries that are parties to these conventions. However, research indicates that discrimination against migrants does exist and that they experience social and economic inequality (Pittaway & Bartolomei, 2001; Buitelaar, 2006; Ludvig, 2006; Aksoy, 2010; Kosnick, 2011; Bell, Valenta & Strabac, 2021; Erat & Demirci, 2022). Although there are significant differences between countries in terms of migrants’ housing conditions, housing disadvantages are widespread and often severe (EU, 2005). Studies in some European countries show that employment and housing standards applied to locals are not applied to migrants, leading to problems of social exclusion (Aksoy, 2010; Bekar, 2018; Erat & Demirci, 2022; Sönmez, 2025).

There is also anti-Muslim sentiment alongside the current anti-immigrant sentiment in European countries. Anti-Muslim sentiment is more widespread than anti-immigrant sentiment and negative attitudes are increasing in Europe (Bell, Valenta & Strabac, 2021). The rising overt hostility towards Islam and Muslim minorities in Western societies has prompted academics to use the term ‘Islamophobia’. Research shows that Europeans’ attitudes towards Muslims tend to be more hostile than their attitudes towards other immigrant minorities (Strabac & Listhaug, 2008; Kaya, 2015; Bansak, Hainmueller & Hangartner, 2016; Storm, Sobolewska & Ford, 2017; Gorodzeisky & Semyonov, 2019; Weichselbaumer, 2019; Abbas, 2019; Bell, Valenta & Strabac, 2021).

In many countries, particularly in Europe, racism, xenophobia, Islamophobia and intolerance towards the ‘other’ are on the rise (Bekar, 2018; Weichselbaumer, 2019). There has been an increase in hate crimes against Muslims, particularly following the terrorist attacks of 11 September 2001 in the United States (ADC-RI9, 2008; Esposito & Kalin, 2011).

In societies where Islamophobia and discrimination or prejudice against immigrants are prevalent, individuals may develop a perception of being subjected to discriminatory treatment. *Per-*

ceived discrimination refers to an individual’s belief that they are being discriminated against due to their physical characteristics, preferences, tendencies, or their ethnic, cultural or religious affiliations (Sanchez & Brock, 1996; Montes, 2010).

Perceived discrimination is a significant source of stress. Individuals who perceive themselves as targets of discrimination tend to employ cognitive avoidance strategies. The level of stress to which individuals are exposed may vary, and the coping strategies they develop may also differ accordingly (Lahoz & Forns, 2016).

Figure 1. *Acculturation Process Model,*

Source: Berry, 1997

Berry’s (1997) acculturation model demonstrates that acculturation is a multidimensional process shaped by both societal and personal factors. The level of adaptation among migrants is determined by the coping strategies they employ as well as the attitudes of the host society. According to this model, illustrated in Figure 1, individuals actively manage the acculturation process through the coping strategies they develop.

The literature examining behavioral changes and coping strategies associated with perceived discrimination remains rather limited. Findings from a study investigating the effects of perceived discrimination and coping mechanisms on the well-being and mental health of newly arrived migrants

indicate that these individuals do perceive themselves as being subjected to discrimination and develop various strategies to avoid it. Observations show that, in order to cope with perceived discrimination, individuals employ behavioral strategies such as Westernization or cultural assimilation, constructing a positive public image, avoiding going out or avoiding going out alone, ignoring or not responding to discriminatory acts, and engaging in social isolation (Gabarrell-Pascuet et al., 2023).

3.1. Being Muslim in Western Europe

Anti-Muslim sentiment and Islamophobia are increasing significantly in Western Europe (Weichselbaumer, 2019; Abbas, 2019). When examining the types of official complaints made by Muslims to public institutions alleging discrimination: Claims of mistrust, harsher treatment, neglect, obstruction and harassment are the reasons behind Muslim minorities' perceptions of discrimination. A significant portion of the complaints are directed at education, the judiciary, social services, health and social security services (Bursell, 2018). A study conducted in Western Europe examined the experiences of discrimination among Muslim minorities, focusing on the circumstances that shape perceptions of discrimination. It was found that daily experiences such as being stopped by the police, verbal abuse or disrespectful treatment in public contribute to perceptions of discrimination (Brüß, 2008).

Anti-Islam sentiment and prejudice and discrimination against Muslim immigrants in 30 European countries have two main causes: domestic and international. The first reason is national policies aimed at the integration of Muslim immigrants in Europe. The second reason is international events beyond the control of European states, such as political turmoil and terrorist attacks in the East. These reasons trigger discrimination against Muslims within the country (Strabac & Listhaug, 2008). Prejudice and discrimination against ethnic and religious groups are not uniform. Across 20 countries in Europe, the level of opposition to Muslim and Jewish immigrants from different races/ethnic groups is hierarchical. Prejudice against Muslims does not extend to other members of the same ethnic/racial group. Prejudice against Jews, on the other hand, is negligible (Gorodzeisky & Semyonov, 2019). Since 2018, there have been a total of 387 cases of discrimination against Muslims in London. The results of a study conducted on a sample of 1,503 Muslims living in the United Kingdom show that 69% of Muslims have been subjected to bullying and harassment in the workplace because of their religious identity, had their religious items (articles of faith) stolen and suffered verbal and physical attacks (Welsh, 2022). It is observed that applicants who wear Muslim religious identifiers are most likely to be employed in low-status jobs, while they are least employable for high-status jobs (Ghuman & Jackson, 2008).

The findings of a study examining discrimination against black and Muslim minority groups in 20 different labour markets indicate that racial and ethnic discrimination has an impact on employment. According to the study's results, Muslim minority groups face more discrimination than other

minority groups (Thijssen et al., 2022). A study conducted in the labour market examines the disadvantage faced by Muslim minorities among second-generation immigrants. The research findings indicate that discrimination against Muslim minorities exists in the labour market. According to the research results, the likelihood of a Muslim candidate being called back for an interview is 2.5 times lower than that of a Christian candidate (Adida, Laitin & Valfort, 2010). A study conducted in the real estate sector analyses the impact of North African Muslims on recruitment. The study created six distinct profiles and found that a total of 1,800 applications were made for 300 job advertisements. According to the findings and results of the research, there is significant hiring discrimination against applicants of North African origin, regardless of their religious affiliation and against Muslim applicants, regardless of their national origin (Pierné, 2013). The results of a multinational field experiment conducted in Germany, the Netherlands, Norway, Spain and the United Kingdom show that religion has a negative effect on recruitment; indeed, this discrimination increases when closeness to Islam is explicitly stated on the job application form (Di Stasio et al., 2019).

3.2. Being a Muslim Woman Who Wears a Headscarf in Western Europe

There is a perception that Muslim minorities in Western Europe face discrimination due to their religious identity (Afshar, 2008; Zempi & Chakraborti, 2015; Trittler, 2018; Khan, 2022; Ke-baïli & Lépinard, 2024). It should not be forgotten that an individual’s awareness of being subjected to discrimination is the first condition for preventing discrimination (Künüroğlu, Acar & Dönmez, 2021). In this respect, measuring individuals’ perceptions of discrimination is an important area of research.

In addition to being an ethnic minority in Europe, Muslim women who wear religious clothing are highly visible and easily identifiable as Muslim, which can make them even more vulnerable (*The Euro-Mediterranean Women’s Foundation* [EMWF], 2018). Muslim women are generally more visible in society than Muslim men. Muslim men’s clothing is more similar to or more easily adaptable to today’s secular or Western lifestyle than that of Muslim women.

An external sign of piety, such as the headscarf, is not compulsory for men. This situation highlights the religious identity of Muslim women in society more than that of Muslim men. The World Conference Against Racism document states that racial and gender discrimination does not always affect men and women equally or in the same way, that women are subject to multiple discrimination and that this is unacceptable. However, any attempts to force women belonging to any faith or religious group to renounce their cultural and religious identity, to restrict their legitimate expression, or to discriminate against women in terms of education and employment opportunities are condemned (United Nations, 2001). In addition to being an ethnic and religious minority in Europe, Muslim women who wear religious clothing are highly visible and easily identifiable as Muslim, which makes them even more vulnerable. Headscarf bans impose an unjust restriction on the lives

of Muslim migrant women, who already face high levels of discrimination. Discrimination against Muslim migrant women must be viewed from an intersectional perspective.

The attitudes of non-Muslim locals living in European countries towards the headscarf are generally negative. Approximately one-quarter of locals oppose Muslims, while approximately two-thirds oppose women wearing headscarves (Helbling, 2014). According to another study, 60 per cent of Germans support the ban on headscarves in public spaces (Van der Noll, 2010). While anti-Muslim sentiments are on the rise in many European countries, the discrimination faced by Muslim women due to their religious attire is not at the same level in every country. According to the EMWF report, only nine of the 28 European Union member states (France, Belgium, Austria, Bulgaria, Denmark, Germany, Italy, Spain and the Netherlands) impose restrictions on the religious clothing worn by Muslim women. In 13 countries, there are reports of institutional/private bans or de facto bans. In six countries, there are no proposals to ban headscarves/veils (EMWF, 2018). The rulings of the Court of Justice of the European Union, including those on headscarves, support discrimination and prohibition. In its decision 128/21 dated 15 July 2021, the Court of Justice ruled that religious symbols, including headscarves, can be banned in the workplace, stating that employers can ban religious symbols in order to appear impartial to their customers or to prevent potential disputes (European Court of Justice, 2021).

The Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe, in its report No. 12956 dated 11 June 2012, entitled “Multiple discrimination against Muslim women in Europe: a report on equal opportunities”, Muslim women in Council of Europe member states face multiple discrimination as women, as members of a religious minority and, in some cases, as persons of migrant origin. As their religious beliefs are seen as the sole defining feature of their identity, they are often victims of stereotyping (Ghumman & Ryan, 2013; Council of Europe, 2012; Council of Europe, 2016). When a woman’s identities as ‘Muslim’ and ‘migrant’ converge, a new identity emerges. The multiple discrimination faced by migrant Muslim women becomes dangerous in their lives, increasing their vulnerability and exposing them to risks (Pittaway & Pittaway 2004; Paz & Kook, 2020). In addition to migration and social gender, the religious element affects both the intensity of the pressure they are subjected to and their ability to respond to it (Paz & Kook, 2020).

A comparative study conducted across eight European countries—Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Sweden and the United Kingdom—examines the impact of hate crimes and Islamophobia on Muslim women. The findings of the study indicate that Muslim women suffer inequality because of their gender, just like other women, but that their religious or ethnic identity exacerbates and deepens this discrimination. In most European countries, Muslim women, especially if they wear a headscarf, are exposed to Islamophobic hate speech. In over 90% of Islamophobic incidents in the Netherlands and 80% in France, the majority of Muslim women who suffer discrimination and attacks wear a visible religious symbol (Council of Europe, 2016).

The integration of migrants into the labour market is as important as their socio-cultural integration. In an applied research study, job applications were made using three fictional female characters with the same qualifications (native German, non-headscarf-wearing migrant, headscarf-wearing migrant). The findings of the study revealed a high level of discrimination against female migrants (Weichselbaumer, 2016). Another study examining whether wearing a headscarf increases discrimination against migrant women found that Muslim women of migrant origin who wear headscarves have much lower employment chances than local women. Discrimination against female migrant headscarf wearers increases further when they wear headscarves in their job application documents, migrant identity cards and photographs (Weichselbaumer, 2019). Another study found that women who wear headscarves are rejected more quickly or accepted more slowly in human resources recruitment compared to women who do not wear headscarves (Unkelbach et al., 2010). It has been concluded that wearing the headscarf, which is part of Muslim identity, is an obstacle to women’s professional success or employment (Fernández-Reino, Di Stasio & Veit, 2022).

Regardless of whether it concerns employment, education or social life, previous studies have shown that Muslim women are generally subjected to very different forms of discrimination based on gender, racism and Islamophobia. These multiple and inseparable identities transform Muslim women into ‘others’ in Western societies. Migrant Muslim women who wear headscarves are aware that they have to endure discrimination because of the high visibility of their headscarves. Nevertheless, they continue to define wearing the headscarf as empowering their personal actions, enabling them to have control over their lives in the public sphere and facilitating their integration into society despite all the difficulties (Paz & Kook, 2020).

4. FINDINGS

The perception of social exclusion, prejudice and discrimination experienced by women wearing headscarves, as revealed in scientific research are consistent with the findings of this study (Afshar, 2008; Unkelbach et al., 2010; Zempi & Chakraborti, 2015; Weichselbaumer, 2016; Weichselbaumer, 2019; Allen, 2021; Fernández-Reino, Di Stasio & Veit, 2022; Khan, 2022; Kebaïli & Lépinard, 2024; Sönmez, 2025). Studies revealing the general discrimination faced by Muslims in the United Kingdom (Hopkins, 2010) also show that Muslim women who wear the niqab are stigmatized, criminalized, and viewed as “dangerous” to British/Western values. Findings from a study conducted with Muslim women who wear the niqab in the UK indicate that wearing the niqab is understood by participants as a personal choice and an expression of religiosity, while also being perceived as a form of agency and a sign of non-conformity to Western consumerist culture and lifestyle (Zempi, 2016). In this context, women who wear the niqab in the United Kingdom are perceived -as well as perceive themselves- as incompatible with the dominant lifestyle of the wider society. Scientific research and field studies show that Muslim immigrant women wearing headscarves face discrimination across the United Kingdom, as in other European countries. The fact that Muslim women choose

to wear clothing that makes their Muslim identity visible, particularly the headscarf, makes their identity more apparent in public and may increase their likelihood of facing discrimination.

In the observational study conducted in Birmingham, it was observed that Muslim women who wear headscarves have developed daily life practices and taken personal precautions to avoid this discrimination or minimise it as much as possible. Six Muslim women wearing headscarves were observed during the approximately three-month observational study conducted as part of the research. The women observed were in Birmingham for educational purposes and had come from Saudi Arabia, Qatar and Egypt. Interviews with the Muslim women examined why they chose Birmingham, why some women wore masks covering their nose and mouth and whether they had adopted a different dress code from that in their home countries, using observational methods.

4.1. Muslim Migrant Women Living Under the Shadow of Discrimination: Observations from Birmingham

Firstly, it has been observed that six Muslim women chose Birmingham on the grounds that it is a city with a large Muslim population. Birmingham is home to the second largest Muslim population in the United Kingdom. According to available data, approximately 27% of the city's total population is Muslim (Figure 2). This percentage is well above the United Kingdom average. Birmingham is known as the 'capital of jihad' (Miller & Rodger, 2019; Allen, 2021). The Muslim population living in Birmingham is quite diverse in terms of ethnic origin (Isakjee, 2012). The graph below shows the 50 UK parliamentary constituencies with the highest proportion of Muslim population aged 18 and over as of 4 July 2024. According to the data, Birmingham is the city where the Muslim population is both the most concentrated (50.3%) and the most widespread (5 different constituencies in the top 11). This situation demonstrates ethnic clustering on a broad urban scale.

Figure 2. Parliamentary Constituencies by Percentage of Muslim

Source: Muslim Council of Britain, 2025.

The research revealed that when the women observed in the study considered which city they wanted to live in before arriving in the United Kingdom, the Muslim population in that city was a decisive factor. When the reasons for this were examined, it was found that the main reasons were feeling more at home or experiencing less discrimination compared to other regions.

Secondly, it was understood that all the women observed adopted a style of dress that differed from that of their home countries. In particular, it was observed that Saudi Muslim women wore loose-fitting, one-piece garments similar to the long black dress in their home countries, but that they changed this style of dress in the United Kingdom. It was observed that women preferred trousers, jackets and more colourful clothing. When examining the reasons for this change in clothing preferences, it was found that the main reasons were not to be seen as “the other” in the society they were in and not to be conspicuous. It can be said that while women did not stop wearing headscarves, they adopted a style closer to the clothing preferences of the locals.

Thirdly, there is the use of masks that cover part of the face. Saudi Muslim women in particular use cloth or surgical masks. They state that in their countries they use a type of face covering called a ‘veil’ that covers all or part of the face and that they do not wish to wear the veil in the United Kingdom. Upon examining their reasons, it has been observed that these women perceive that wearing a niqab increases the likelihood of facing discrimination or prejudice. To avoid prejudice or discrimination, women prefer surgical or cloth masks that cover the face instead of the niqab. Veiled Muslim women are aware that the niqab is perceived as incompatible with the established culture and lifestyle in Western societies (Zempi, 2016). In response to the prejudice and discrimination that may arise from this perceived incompatibility, women have developed alternative methods of face covering other than the niqab.

Of course, these observations do not cover all Muslim women who wear headscarves living in the United Kingdom. The observations were made in a limited environment but are based on real experiences. It is possible that these experiences may not occur in sample groups in other parts of the United Kingdom and that other types of experiences may also occur in addition to these experiences. Based on the available observational evidence, it has been seen that Muslim women wearing headscarves who come to Birmingham for educational purposes take their own precautions against prejudice and discrimination. It is recommended that future studies address strategies for coping with perceived discrimination from a broader perspective and focus particularly on the dimension of social relationships. Although this research could not focus on a common social network among participants due to the limited and homogeneous structure of the sample group, important clues were obtained regarding how individual social relationships were shaped by perceived discrimination.

5. CONCLUSION

This study examined racial and religious discrimination in European contexts by focusing on Muslim identity, irrespective of race, with particular attention to headscarf-wearing Muslim immigrant women whose religious visibility renders them more exposed to prejudice and exclusion. Building on existing research demonstrating that Muslim immigrant women in Western Europe frequently perceive and experience discrimination -including verbal and physical harassment- this study explored the everyday practices developed by headscarf-wearing Muslim women in Birmingham in response to such experiences.

The findings reveal that the observed women employ a range of adaptive strategies that shape their daily lives. One recurring theme concerns the preference of some women to wear surgical masks instead of the niqab, reflecting an awareness of the stigma attached to face veiling and a conscious effort to minimise negative social encounters. Another prominent theme is the perception of Birmingham -due to its relatively large Muslim population- as a safer and more inclusive urban environment in which integration can be experienced with fewer barriers. The city is not only perceived as a place of belonging but also as a space that women are reluctant to leave, even temporarily, because of the sense of safety it provides.

In addition, the study shows a shift in clothing practices, whereby participants move away from full-length, monochrome garments commonly worn in their countries of origin towards more layered and relatively colourful attire in the host context. These practices illustrate how headscarf-wearing Muslim women actively negotiate visibility and manage perceived risks in public space. Rather than being passive responses, these strategies reflect forms of agency through which women adapt to and navigate discriminatory environments.

By situating these everyday practices within broader debates on migration, Islamophobia, and social exclusion in Western Europe, this article contributes to a deeper understanding of how Muslim migrant women perceive, experience, and negotiate their social realities in contemporary Britain. The experiences of headscarf-wearing women highlight a central paradox of multicultural societies: while processes of othering persist, those positioned as *'the other'* simultaneously challenge and re-shape dominant meanings of identity and belonging through their everyday practices.

Etik Kurul Onayı: Bu makale etik kurul onayı gerektirmemektedir.

Hakem Değerlendirmesi: Çift kör hakem.

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GENİŞLETİLMİŞ TÜRKÇE ÖZET

Bu çalışma, İngiltere’nin Birmingham şehrinde yaşayan başörtülü Müslüman göçmen kadınların algılanan ayrımcılıkla başa çıkmak amacıyla geliştirdikleri günlük yaşam pratiklerini incelemektedir. Araştırma, Müslüman kadınların gündelik yaşamlarında karşılaştıkları farklı ayrımcılık biçimleriyle nasıl başa çıktıklarına odaklanmaktadır. Bu araştırma, uluslararası öğrencilerin katıldığı bir İngilizce dil kursunda doğal gözlem yöntemi kullanılarak gerçekleştirilmiştir. Gözlemsel araştırma, araştırmacının olguya müdahale etmeden doğal bağlamda davranışları gözlemlemesine ve bu davranışlarla ilgili olayları sistematik olarak kaydetmesine olanak tanıyan bir yaklaşımdır. Anketler veya görüşmeler gibi yaygın araştırma teknikleri, genellikle davranışın gerçekleştiği bağlamdan kopuktur ve davranışın anlık süreçlerini, karşılaşmalarını veya uygulamalarını yakalamada yetersiz kalabilmektedir. Buna karşın, gözlemsel araştırma, davranışların doğal ortamları ve ilişkisel bağlamları içinde ayrıntılı bir şekilde incelenmesine olanak tanımaktadır. Gözlemsel araştırma yöntemi kullanılan bu çalışmada, kadınların algıladıkları önyargı ve ayrımcılık deneyimlerine karşı geliştirdikleri baş etme pratikleri analiz edilmektedir. Araştırma, “Gözlemlenen davranışların arkasındaki bağlam nedir?” sorusu etrafında şekillenmektedir ve bu soruya yanıt aranmıştır.

Gözlemler, Birleşik Krallık’ın Birmingham kentinde uluslararası öğrencilerin katıldığı bir İngilizce dil kursunda gerçekleştirilmiştir. Çalışmada, aynı kursa kayıtlı ve başörtüsü takan altı Müslüman kadına odaklanıldı. Bu kadınların benzer kültürel ve dini geçmişlere sahip olmaları, benzer günlük pratikler geliştirmeleri ve kamusal görünürlük açısından ortak sosyal konumları paylaşmaları, onları uyumlu bir gözlem grubu haline getirdi. Katılımcılar, araştırmacı tarafından kurs içindeki doğal etkileşimler yoluyla belirlendi; örneklem grubu, ortak davranış kalıplarının gelişmesi nedeniyle tek bir gözlem birimi olarak ele alındı. Bazı katılımcılar birbirlerini tanıyor olsalar da grup genel olarak birbirleriyle iletişim halinde değildi; bu nedenle örneklem ortaklığı, paylaşılan kimlik ve benzer pratiklere dayanıyordu. Gözlem süresi boyunca, davranışların zaman içinde tutarlı mı yoksa duruma bağlı mı olduğunu ve bağlamlara göre nasıl değiştiği üç ay boyunca hafta içi her gün 09.00 – 12.00 saatleri arasında sistematik olarak izlenmiştir. Katılımcıların belirli davranışları nasıl yorumladıkları, uygulamalarını sürdürmelerinin altında yatan nedenleri ve bu uygulamaları şekillendiren motivasyonları hakkında fikir edinmek için doğal olarak ortaya çıkan günlük konuşmalar gerçekleştirilmiştir.

Doğrudan gözlemler ve resmi olmayan sohbetlerden elde edilen bulgular, bazı başörtülü kadınların peçe yerine cerrahi maske ya da yüzün ağız kısmını örten maske kullanmayı tercih ettiklerini ortaya koymaktadır. Bu tercih, kadınların olası önyargıların farkında olduklarını ve olumsuz sosyal karşılaşmaları en aza indirmeye yönelik stratejiler geliştirdiklerini göstermektedir. Katılımcılar, görece yüksek Müslüman nüfusa sahip bir şehir olan Birmingham’ı, entegrasyonun daha az engelle deneyimlenebildiği, daha güvenli ve kapsayıcı bir ortam olarak algılamaktadır. Bu sebeple, kadınlar tarafından yaşam alanı olarak Birmingham şehrinin bilinçli bir tercih olduğu ifade edilmektedir. Kadınların, daha güvenli buldukları bu kentten seyahat amacıyla dahi ayrılmak istemedikleri gözlem-

lenmiştir. Menşe ülkelerinde tek parça ve koyu renkli kıyafetleri tercih ettiklerini belirten kadınlar, İngiltere’de ise parçalı ve daha renkli kıyafetleri tercih ettiklerini ifade etmektedir. Bu pratikler, kadınlar tarafından algılanan ayrımcılığa yanıt olarak geliştirilen gündelik başa çıkma yöntemleri olarak değerlendirilmektedir. Elde edilen bulgular, kadınların başörtüsü ve peçeye karşı olan önyargı ve ayrımcılık ifade eden tutumlardan haberdar oldukları göstermesi bakımından literatürü desteklemektedir. Bununla birlikte, kadınların algıladıkları bu ayrımcılığa karşı bir baş etme pratikleri geliştirdiklerini görülmüştür. Çalışma, bu gündelik pratikleri Avrupa’daki göç, İslamofobi ve toplumsal dışlanma tartışmaları çerçevesinde ele alarak, Müslüman göçmen kadınların İngiltere’deki toplumsal gerçekliklerini nasıl algıladıklarına ve bu gerçekliklerle nasıl müzakere ettiklerine dair daha derinlemesine bir anlayış sunmaktadır. Bulgular, başörtülü Müslüman göçmen kadınların Müslümanlara yönelik önyargı ve ayrımcılığın farkında olduklarını ve gündelik yaşamlarında olumsuz deneyimleri azaltmak amacıyla -kendi kimliklerini koruyarak- görünürlüğü yönetmeye yönelik uyumlayıcı stratejiler geliştirdiklerini göstermektedir.

Bilimsel araştırmalar ve saha çalışmaları, başörtüsü takan Müslüman göçmen kadınların, diğer Avrupa ülkelerinde olduğu gibi Birleşik Krallık’ta da ayrımcılığa maruz kaldıklarını göstermektedir. Bilimsel araştırmalarda ortaya konulan, başörtüsü takan kadınların maruz kaldığı sosyal dışlanma, önyargı ve ayrımcılık algısı, bu çalışmada elde edilen bulgular ile tutarlıdır. Birleşik Krallık’ta Müslümanların maruz kaldığı genel ayrımcılığı ortaya koyan çalışmalar peçe giyen Müslüman kadınların damgalandığını, suçlu muamelesi gördüğünü ve İngiliz/Batı değerleri için “tehlikeli” olarak görüldüğünü de göstermektedir. Bu bağlamda, Birleşik Krallık’ta peçe giyen kadınlar, toplumun baskın yaşam tarzıyla uyumsuz olarak algılandıkları algısına sahiptir. Sıralanan ayrımcılık ve uyumsuzluğa ilişkin tüm olumsuz algılar kadınların baş etme stratejileri geliştirmelerine neden olmaktadır.

Elbette gözlemler sonucu elde edilen bulgular, Birleşik Krallık’ta yaşayan ve başörtüsü takan tüm Müslüman kadınları kapsamamaktadır. Gözlemler sınırlı bir ortamda yapılmış olmakla birlikte gerçek deneyimlere dayanmaktadır. Bu deneyimlerin, Birleşik Krallık’ın diğer bölgelerindeki örnek gruplarda yaşanmayabileceği kadar bu deneyimlere ek olarak başka tür deneyimlerin yaşanabileceği mümkündür. Gelecekte gerçekleştirilecek çalışmaların, algılanan ayrımcılıkla başa çıkma stratejilerini daha geniş bir perspektiften ele alması ve özellikle sosyal ilişkiler boyutuna odaklanması önerilmektedir. Bu araştırma kapsamında, örneklem grubunun sınırlı ve homojen yapısı nedeniyle katılımcıların sosyal ilişki ağına odaklanılamamış olsa da kurulan bireysel sosyal ilişkilerin algılanan ayrımcılık tarafından şekillendiğine dair önemli ipuçları elde edilmiştir. Sonuç olarak, mevcut gözlem kanıtlarına dayanarak, eğitim amacıyla Birmingham’a gelen başörtüsü takan Müslüman kadınların algıladıkları önyargı ve ayrımcılığa karşı kendi önlemlerini aldıkları görülmüştür.

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